

trsubjza& cE&q;

Ogogatmi f

pmvrf t u f

polawoepmvrfwfi b&m; [E&wlu f wfi y, fzu&wvrfcbn h aum" trsu f
 x&u jci f w&m; ES h vu u l l f x m; usi b&wvrfcbn on h cE&bn f c jci f w&m; w l l
 ta l u mi f u l l v r f n e&az m f y x m; y g o n / trsu x&u jci f \ t j y p E S h trsu l u b j y a p E l l & e f
 a q; o z G f t o l l y f E l l h o m c E l l b n f c j c i f w&m; w l l t a l u mi f E S h o n f c j c i f \ t u s f?
 o n f r c j c i f \ t j y p w l t a l u mi f y # u w f a w m f r s m; x f D y r m? O y a r, s r s m; j z i h v u l v s f
 r l b r o a z m f x k w i w i f y x m; y g o n / a q; u l l & m * g r j z p f r b M u l l w i l u m u G f x m; o i f o u b l l
 r f t l c E i m w l f a v m b? a' g o? a r m [w n f [h o m u d v o m a & m * g r s f w l l r w l l r a y g u f
 & a t m i f c E l l q; u l l o h p b i f a l u mi f t M u l l y k w i f y x m; o n h p m v r f w p l a p m i f j z p y g o n /

edgef

[auma"m twHe Zmemw] -] MurfMuKwaom trsuba' goonf tu&ta l u mi f
 t q l l t a u mi f u l l o f (Zm? |? 3/ 97? 218-219/ ' D |? 1/ 52/) [b n E S h t n d a' g o o n f
 r r p w l l r x e f c y E l l b o j z i h t a u mi f t q l r c j c m; E l l l o l p l v a p & m v l u r d r f r; w w l o j z i h
 t j y p j z p l w w y g o n / c E l l o n f c j c i f w&m; u l l m v u l l f x m; r n b q l y g u u l l h y g; j z i h
 t j y p r s m; u l l u s; v e f E l l r n i r [k w y g / , i f E S h y w o u f i j r w p o b b & m; & S N v u f, m & h
 t * m O u j z p a o m t & S f o m & y k w & m r a x & f r w l u b u t r s u b j z w & m; i g; y g; u l l v l u e m o i h
 a l l u mi f a t m u l y g t w l l f a [m l u m; a w m f r c y g o n /

- 1/ trit usi f raumi faomvnf Elwx&u&raumi f o j z p y g u Elwx&u&raumi f r l u b m, l i
 trsubjz&ef
- 2/ Elwx&u&raumi faomvnf trit usi f aumi f y g u aumi faom trit usi f u b m, l i
 trsubjz&ef
- 3/ trit usi f E S E l l w x & u E p c k w l l r a u mi f o j z p y g u & l t g E p l o u z G & l o m t m & l u l l q i j c i f
 i trsubjz&ef
- 4/ trit usi f E l l w x & u E S & l t g E p l o u z G f t m & l y g r & l o j z p y g u v n f y p l y e f o b & m E p j z m
 v l u O e a v; E l l b o j z p a o m a l u mi h o e m; u & l p m o u f i trsubjz&ef
- 5/ trit usi f E l l w x & u E p c k w l l r a u mi f j y b M u n E l z G E p l o u z G f t m & l y g & l o u l l i
 w p b o u f y w v l l & e f i z l e f r v l l u mi f? E p l o u p h a y g i f o i f t y a l u mi f (y g & m, e? 40-

* a' gu l v m? w l z u l y g a r m u? t a & w l l f y n m x m e? y l c t; w u i o l l /

t m; xkw r n q l v s i f a v m b ? a ' g o ? a r m [p a o m u d v o m w & m ; r s m ; u l e t r f j y d w & m ; x t w & m ; j r w r f s m ; u h & & l u m r * z l v e a h e b o l r s u a r s i u f y k e h r n f j z p l y g o n /

[c e d y & r h w a y g w l v u m) [l q b n h t w l f] o n t c j c i f o n i j r w a o m t u s i h y i f l z p l y g o n / (' 0 2 / 4 2 /) (c l 1 / 4 1 /)] c e d } & f s o m v g i o l v ? o r m ' d y n m p o n t w l u h & & e h l y d a v m u d a v m u k v & m e s j z m v h w g f a t m i j r i b l w p d d j z p e h f a y r n / ' c e d v & m ; v u u d b x m ; r s o m v g i t & m & m w g i a t m i j r i e h r n f l z p l y g o n / x h a m u m i b o n t c j c i f [h o m c e d] o n i b o w g i a t m i j r i m b l w l f o w j y k u s i b o h o i h a o m v & m ; v n f j z p l y g o n / c e d n o a b m v u p m r n o w d g o c f j & w l \ t l y p e s h a w o u u k i f q h & a o m t c g w g i o n t c j c i f j z p l i t r s u a ' g o r x l u f c i f a l u m i h] t a ' g o } [k a c : o n h u b l v a p w o l u f w p c k v n f j z p a p y g o n / w y r u t r h & f c i f a l u m i h] t a v m b } u l v n f j z p a p y g o n /] c e d } o n i o a w m a u m i f w & m ; j z p o j z i h v l u f e m u s i b o h x l u v a y o n / o n t c b o n i [k q l m u b & m ; a v m i f r s v p y g ; y l x z o l w l \ o n t c e h p e f t m ; o n i r s m ; a o m t m ; j z i h t w l f t w m & w w y g o n / t w l f t w m x u i a u s t v e l m v g i o n t f r c e h m u b l v u l w y e r w w a o m a l u m i h o l t j y p l u u h h t j y p j z p l u m ' l u y i v , h a o m u & a v o n / e p d d e s z u f t u s t r & d j z p l u & o n /

t j y n j y n f q h & m a x & o g ' w u i o l v y g a r m u e s y l q & m a w m f a ' g u l v m e e r m v m b o h b r a x & j r w l u j a ' g o x l u l y d a w m h v l u t m u l v a e w , ? o l l a o m i j y e a w m r a j y m b t j y e a w m r v l y b t j q l v m r s t u h ' l u a e l c e d [k a c : l u a o m v n f ? u l b h y g ; t e u f r a e m u h [k q h t y a o m]] p d v y h [q h & m u w l e j y e a e a o m a l u m i h c e d t p p r [k v a l u m i f } r e l l q l x m ; y g o n /

t & s d v m o * 3 / 4 a a m ' t h i l q & m a w m u v n f o n t c h v m e l a t m i t e l v m r w h a l u m i f ? o n t c h v m u] t a ' g o u b l v j z p l y d a t m i t e l v m u a ' g o t u b l v j z p a l u m i f ? o n t c j c i f o n i p d v \ t & n f t a o g r s m ; w u l v m e h l a p a l u m i f ? a t m i t e j c i f o n i p d v x l w g f y a v m i b n y d m u m v m v g i a ' g o t p h f t c e s h t n t m c m w t j z p a j y m i f o h ; w w l y d t e & m , i m u d v s y g o n / a v m u w g i o n t f r c e h j c i f [h o m a ' g o a l u m i h j y p r i t r s t r s t u s ; v e a e m u a l u m i f ? o n t c h m u b o n h t w l u f & e b l t j z p f a & m u r o h ; b l n i t f c s r f w h v r l y w d e f u s i f u h w n a q m u e h a l u m i f u l v n f o j r i e h l y g o n / o n t c j c i f e s h y w b o u r i r o l a w m r s m ; u o n t c e h h a o m o l r s m ; u h v b a y s n l v i n h [k i f w w l y d o l a w m a u m i f a w l u o n t c e h f r s t j r w l q h w & m ; u l u s i b o h e h i o l [k t j r i f t r s t r s d u f y m ; w w a l u m i f r e d u m ; c l y g o n /

o l a w o e o r m * 3 / 4 y o h u s r f u c e e s h o a y u m \ x t j c m ; c s u l u d a z n f y & m w g i [c e d] [b n f o u & w l u r d t m ; u h ? e l w l w l z i h x d y g ; y k w t w l r j y k v m a o m v n f a ' g o j z i h , i f y k w l v t m ; p d v q h j c i f ? j y e l e j y p r h ; j c i f ? x d y g ; y k w t w l v u p m ; a c j c i f r j y k o l o n t c h a e h j c i f e s b o u r h w l u r l u h e s p y a o m t c r t y & m o d w l \ ' p l t o w f t p m ; a e & m w l \ m u r t w r f c u l x e f c i f ? r j y n p j c i f p o n i w e s h a w o u u k a o m t c g j a ' g r e o } p d v q i f & j c i f ? p d v e s h r c s r f a j r j c i f w l u h r j z p a p b l o n t c e h j c i f y i j z p j y d w p e n t t m ; l z i h] t a ' g o a p w o l u j v n f l z p l y g o n /] o a y u m \ o a b m r n e | m & (a c :) v l t s i p & m ? c i r i p & m ? c s p p & m ? e s b o u f r w e h p & m t m & m s e s h a w l q l h a o m f o m , m c i r i f v l t s i f w y r u f p l v r f j c i f j z p a o m w p h ? o y g ' g e f b u b l y g r a & m u a t m i f a p m i h & s u f w m ; q d x m ; e h f r v p l v d j c i f o a b m e s h t e d m & j z p a o m r e f p & m ? & p & m ? r c l t s i p & m ? p d v q h p & m t m / 2 h t r s t r w e s h a w o u u k i f q h l v m & o n h t c g r s m ; u v n f & h l e f j c i f ? p d v q h a ' g o j z p j c i f

bubol ra&mu&apbl apmi h&snufvm; qDxm; Ehlrl vspv&l&ci foabmwpr&tyif jzpbol/
 xltjyif xblom £ |m& ted ml&lb, lbuul&syg? rvulobl cprlefyg tv, ftvwl
 oabmtolulqmi bnh jwlvwrZ&v&mapwouf uyliv&f Oayum [k ac:q&lyg
 onf/ (ok-or& *%? 380-381/) c&ES h Oayum&w&E&fyg; v&ul v&ul&fxm; Ehlrl v&f
 tvep&wat; jr Nilrl&crf&Ehlrl nrl&lp&lygonf

tcef(1)

b&m&tavmi&awm&ES h on&ou&u&dr&m; \c&E&f&f&n&f

ptcef&w&f on&f&cl&f-c&E&g&r&u&ul v&u&aw&j&zn&usi&f&cl&bn&h a*gw&rj&rw&pb&n
 b&m& &S&N tavmi&awm&ob&Or&m; x&r&S aw&r&rif? a&O&ó&E&m& rif&u&u&w&N c&E&g&r&D
 j&zn&usi&f&ly&tr&sm;? c&E&D&g' Z&m&w&r&S b&m& avmi&f&c&E&D&g' &ao&N on&f&cl&yl& q' &eq&ir&if&Z&m&w&r&S
 b&m& avmi&f&q' &eq&ir&if& \on&f&cl&yl& o&cl&yg&v&Z&m&w&r&S b&m& avmi&f o&cl&yg&v e*g&rif& \
 on&f&cl&yl&tr&sm; ES h jr&w&pb&n b&m& &S&N v&u&sn&awm&h t&S&f&om& &v&w&w& \ on&f&cl&yl& t&S&f&yl&P&O
 rax& \on&f&cl&yl&ES h o&u&um; rif& \on&f&cl&yl&tr&sm; u<&u&of&r&w&if&yo&tr; y&gr&nf

tavmi&awm& aw&r&rif&om; on&f& ol&v&sup&u&ul& faom ob&w&a, mu&tr& \ j&cl&f&aj&cm&uf
 r&? r&ef, p&hom&q&i&ES h e&if&ou& &ef j&cl&f&aj&cm&uf? t&q&ly&ifa&om&aj&r&f&zi&h j&cl&f&aj&cm&uf&tr&sm; u<
 aw&ou&u& &aom&t&cg& r&w&er&v&yl& w&n&un&f&it&f&ou&pb&n nu&nu&ul&h on&f&cl&E&h&cl&bn&/ x<&w&l
 pm; aom&u&f&G& &mr&sm;? v&yaom uac&son&tr&sm; j&zi&h j&zm; a, mi&fo&ga&qmi&f&ci&f? & &sp&u&f&q&yl&
 z&G& &maum&ifaom& tq&if? to&ll& te&ll& t&om? taw&u&t&x&d&t&m&tr&sm; u< rv&bm& ra& &ni&f&om
 &if&q&ul& h&aw&ou&u& on&f&cl&cg&v&n&f, a&nu&mu&v&el&v&el&v&yl&f&ci&f? p&w&ES&h& rom&r, nj&zp&f&ci&f? a' go
 tr&su&x&u&f&ci&f&w&u&ul& rj&z&p&ay: ap& &ef r&rl&p&w&ul& y&n&om&P&f&zi&h&e&f&of&tr&f&yl& c&E&g&r&u&ul
 j&zn&q&n&f&cl&u&mi&f (Zm? 2 / 149/ Zm? |? 6 / 1-11/) o&& &yg&onf

a&O&ó&E&m&Z&m&w&awm&w&f tavmi&awm&a&O&ó&E&m&rif&u&u&on&f y&p& q&if&z&lawm&ul
 u&v&f&w&ll&f&oll& v&S' g&ef&v&u&bon&f&w&ul& w&ll&f&oj&n&f&om; r&sm; u p&w&v&f&q&ly& e&ef&awm&r&S
 ES h&kw&f&ci&f&ul&bn&f&cl&um [tr&OE&h&awm&ou&f&yg&awm&i&u& &a&ol&w&f&yl& at; c&r&f&pb&n a&ex&ll&cl&yg
 onf/ x<&ty&if ZZ&um&yl&P&tr; u om; awm&Z&m&v&ES h or&awm&f u&P&n&Z&e&w&ul& t&v&f&cl&bj&zi&h
 u&f&f&tr&z&p&ay; v&f&cl&yl& r&rl& & &w&v&f& om; ES h or&du&ul& E&yp&u&f&um&ac: a&qmi&f&u&ul& j&ri& h&aw&om&v&n&f
 c&P&w&j&z&p&ay: on&h a' g&op&w&ul&bn&f&cl&yl& v&S' g&ef&cl&yl&tr&f&n (Zm? 2/ 312/ Zm? V? 7/ 241/
 p& &d m? V/ 76/) tavmi&awm& \ c&E&g&r&u&ul& j&n&on&h ol&awm&aum&f&p& &u&ul& x&i& &tr&pb&n
 aw&g&ri&E&h&lygonf

qu&v&ul&f &e&w&tr&f&ci&f? v&u± rac&f&ci&f? &e&f&il&tr&z&f&ci&f&e&f&h&rl&u&E&yp&uf& n&of&yr&f
 apm&um; ol&tr&sm; j&y&e&v&n&f&tr&su&r&x&ul&bl on&f&cl&bn&h c&E&D&g' Z&m&w&awm&r&S c&E&D&g' &ao&N
 on&f&cl&yl&u&v&if&yy&gr&nf/ u&v&m&A&ri&f&on&f&cl&E&D&g' &ao&u&ll&tr&su&x&u&f&yl& q&f&wy&f&om&u&ul&f&zi&h
 t&cs&u&w&p&ax&mi& &u&f&ci&f? v&u&z&sm; a&j&cz&sm; r&sm;? ' t&ES h v&u&f&arm&f&tr&sm; u&f&z&w&f&ci&f? v&u&f&arm&f&f&e&f&
 ay&gi& &i&f&ES h&f&ac&g&f&w&ul& o&e&v&su&f&zi&f&zw&um& &i&D&u&ll&za&em&f&zi&h&ay&g&u&f&um& &u& &u&p&u&p&uf
 E&yp&u&f&om&v&n&f tr&su&r&x&ul&bl on&f&cl&yl&u&ul& (Zm? 1? 99/ Zm? |? 3/ 311/) p&Z&m&w&w&f
 t&x&if&t& &tr&aw&E&h&lygonf

t&S fYlPθax&N onf;cyLuH yPθOg' okwēū awQri&Ygon/ t&S fYlPθax&f
 onf olemy&EĀwĪ f;om omoemy/koŋ;a&mu&ef b&M;&S ftm; avsmuŋxm;&m b&M;&S fu
]olemy&EĀwĪ f;om;wĪbnf Murf;MukwctuxefuleN/ tu, fi oi tuH qh&;wĪ f;xθjci f?
 jctf;ajcmufci f? cji f;aygufci f? wkwjzi &Lufci f? "m; jzi f;kwjci f? taooufci f; yMuvSi f
 oi f;tm; rniub; jzprnēt; } [kar; awm rN/ xθt cg t&S fYlPθū]Ew jzi f; qh&; aom t cg
 vufzi f; r&Lufvm awmāo; onf [kvnf; aumi f? wkwjzi &LufSi f; vnf; rowlvm awmāo;
 onf [kvnf; aumi f? tu, fi taoowMuvSi f; vnf; pcEmuH ft ykfaumi Deŋky DelyH
 Muθxrf; aqmi hē& onf; spub; qyji Dai f; zG & n; jzpa omāLumi hēlemy&EĀwĪ f; om; rsm; owfz wĪ
 Mu onf; rñ aus; Z; wi f; zG & n; jz pN [kvnf; aumi f; atmu rñ lqygrñ } (r? 3/ 311/) [k
 avsmuŋxm; jci f; uH Munf; ci f; tm; jzi h t&S fYlPθN onf; cēH pēf; & n; uH twk; zG f awQri f
 eH lYgon/

wzef **o*gxno*θH kv? aOypwvθkvū** oLum; rīf; ES ft o&mw lppf wLū&mwG f
 aOypwvθ o&muH zr; f; c; bn/ to&mrif u oLum; rīf; uH tr; s; r; qh&; ykw; w; onf uH
 onf; cēH omāLumi h rmwv; u; aLumufi onf; cēH e&ygoavm? cēftm; enf; i onf; cēH e&
 ygoavm } [kar; & m oLum; rīf; u-

- olwpyg; a' gox; ubn; ub; a' gojyer; x; ub; a' goji; f; aeon
 a' goji; f; hējci f; onf; i f; v; l; u; l; w; m; j; r; p; E; y; f; u; y; j; ci f; rñāLumi f?
- tu; s; [br; w; w; f; u; f; u; s; om; v; f; t; j; r; w; q; n; j; z; p; y; θ; u; f; u; s; θ; & h; om; w; & m;
 w; l; w; f; onf; c; j; ci f; xuf; y; l; w; e; a; om; u; f; u; s; θ; & h; om; w; & m; [l; r; & n; Lumi f?
 t; m; & b; j; z; p; y; g; v; s; u; f; t; m; r; h; oN; r; aumi f; ajm; q; n; j; y; k; v; y; r; u; l; onf; c; j; ci f; onf
 t; j; r; w; q; n; [ko; l; aw; m; aumi f; w; l; ajm; q; n; u; a; Lumi f?
- u; f; u; l; a' gox; ub; l; u; y; e; f; a' gox; ub; p; w; v; q; n; o; r; ñ; x; l; b; a; t; mu; f; k; w; n; t; b; l;
 om; j; z; p; y; θ; j; y; e; a' gor; x; ub; onf; c; e; H; o; r; ñ; a; t; mi; E; H; c; a; om; p; p; y; u; a; t; mi; f; ol
 j; z; p; a; Lumi f?
- olwpyg; a' gox; ubn; u; l; o; d; s; u; b; onf; c; h; aj; y; n; i; f; t; o; b; n; f; r; h; ES; f; o; l; w; p; y; g;
 E; p; o; θ; v; H; tu; s; u; l; u; s; i; b; n; r; n; ā; Lumi f; (o; H; 1/ 222-224/ o; H; |? 1/ 313/)
&S f; yaompum; rsm; onf; t; v; e; f; s; w; b; m; v; l; u; e; m; z; G; f; aumi f; v; y; gon/

O' get | ux m; v; n; f; cE; g; r; ES; f; y; w; b; u; f; i;] onf; c; h; t; p; e; f; ES; f; y; n; p; b; l; t; z; H
 onf; r; c; e; H; a; om; t; & m; r; n; b; n; f; & H; t; & m; & m; onf; c; e; H; b; n; b; m; } (O' ge? | / 238/) [k
 vnf; aumi f? **olwuθO*? ja [2mv** olvū o; y; θ; y; & A; z; b; n; f; b; & m; ? w; & m; ? o; l; C; m; w; l; u; l;
 u; & l; w; t; s; a; ompum; u; h; j; m; q; & m; b; & m; & S; f; u; & [e; f; w; l; t; m; u; & l; c; & a; om; t; c; g; r; [k; w; n; t; u; l;
 r; [k; v; ā; Lumi f? r; r; e; f; ā; Lumi f; a' gor; x; ub; l; & S; f; j; y; & r; n; f; q; v; i; q; v; f; a; e; u; m; onf; c; y; g; u;
 [k; w; i; f; e; l; onf; [k; o; l; b; j; z; p; p; & m; & h; omāLumi h; u; & l; p; y; p; & m; u; q; v; i; q; v; f; r; a; e; b; l; aj; z; & S; f; ay; & e; f;
 r; e; L; u; m; awm r; y; gon/ (' θ 1/ 1/)

1? 1/ tavmi fawmLūDrsm; cEĀv&m; qijci ES/vb; f; onpēf; & n; f

tavmi fawmLūDrsm; \ cEĀv&m; v; u; f; u; l; b; x; m; y; ES; h; cEĀg; r; ES; v; H; o; f; q; i; j; ci f; y; k;
 w; i; r; ñ; a; t; mu; f; y; g; t; w; l; f; j; z; p; y; gon/

- JpceEInnaomw&m; onf cyloffaom*PausZt\ qellusiboujzponh trsuif a'goull rlvvity, fazmuwwaomallumi h *PausZt; ujnypjci f; u olawmf aumi f; wlt wuf olwpyg; wlrzsuqDEll bonhvuubaumi f; MuD jzpayonf/ }
- olwpyg; uhtypDEll bonh tavmifawmMuDrsm; \ tqilweqmuDvnt; jzpay onf/ trsuxu jcifaum" rduh jidtapwwlonh&t, Ovnt; jzpayonf/ tyg, lvtg; uhl ylvqllumi f; jzponh wltg; &uMuDvnt; jzpay \ / ewjyn? jA [m jynbll wu&mu&muumi f; apmi f; wef; avsum; MuDvnt; jzpayonf/ tvefrwvS onhu? ! Elw? ES; wN piMu, jci f; vnt; jzpay \ / }
- owDgwlonf at; apwwaom onf; chlw&m; uhl vufull fxm; MuBl yavmi ap wwaom trsu&gorsm; uhlbm vufull lkvvlyjyD tm; xkw&eluaomallumi h pbOrsnvnt; yavmi ae&? wrv&pbOrsnvnt; yavmi ae&ygonf/ }
- ou igluh jypfrn; chl vif igcElyg&rES h rjynpDEll bav&m? oN jypfrn; rbnlyif ightwuf cElyg&rDjynhumi f; jzprf oN jypfrn; rbnf igluh usZt; jylci f; yi f jzponf/ }
- onf; jci f; - cElyw&m; &vuf &ebl [li wppwvpa, murO r&Eh f [li vnt; aumi f; ponhll jzpygonf/ b&m; tavmifawm rsm; onf cElyg&rES lywouf pol ES; h o f; Ehl Muojzi ht xwft xyf b&m; tjzpbll a&mu&cMu jci f; jzponf/ }

cElyg&rduh jznhusi qnfy; awm rbaomt cg tavmifawm ojrwl onf Oeclawmrl onhtwll f rclwr, O f onf; clawm r&jci f; wnt [hom **opul'd new&m?** olwptuom; wN trfr; jyl? ajymqtsurfm; twuf ax&mpOfpm; tublvfrsm; rlul y, p&ljci f; [hom **pnf'grd new&m?** trsu&um" xMu&omi f; usefrN jidfat; jci f; wnt [hom **Oyorn'd /new&m?** ynmOmPfi tMuD tjrw&jci f; wnt [hom **yrm'd new&m?** pav; rstaom tust; jzpx&f; tjrwft p&f; xluhull vufawbllaqmi f; clpm; &aomallumi h aemu&emif xyfumxyfumwll cElyg&rDv&m; uhl yfr; rsm; jznhusi lawm rbaonv (r [m? AR yw f; ' lyll f;) / 162-168/) azmfycjydaom tavmifawm ES lvuG omOuMuDrsm; jznhusi clhom cEly onf; jci f; rsm; uhl Mu n jci f; tm; jzi h avmu&vmukwE p jzmaom tust; pbyfr; uhl wlyfr; apEh f aLumi f; o&Eh lygonf/ tcef(2) wof onf; jci f; \ tust; ES tonfr; jci f; jzi h &&Eh rnh tqh tjypfrsm; uhl xyfr lvi fyofr; ygrn/ }

tcef(2)

onf; jci f; \ tust; ES tonfr; jci f; \ tjypf

b&m; &S u onf; jci f; \ tust; (5) yg; ES tonfr; jci f; \ tjyp (5) yg; wll t u p b w l ü atmu f; ygtwll f; a [m l u m; x m; y g o n f / }

onf; jci f; tust; (5) ygrn

- (1) vltrsm; cspci jci f; (2) &frsm; lci f; (3) tjypfrsm; jci f; (u&lp&mu h fr? Elw rbnf; jci f;)
- (4) raw&Obao&lci f; (5) aoaom ewjynh&mu&jci f; ES h

xlenf;wprn ig;&mi g;q, Zmwawmvm zEeZmwawv vnfonf;chf&bl &efi
 zjicifalumi h OIES Nullyiapmi lewvwl touqni ysup&alumi f aw&yg on/
 xZmwawmwf Olni Bullyiatmuwof ttpObullyiull fajcmuf jykvlusi xdwvef
 c&on/ polzp&onlu Bullyiapmi lewfyklylonf [lxityd Bullyiapmi h ewftay:
 &eni k&zon/ wpaewof vnf;bdvlyrnh vuorm;u vnf;bdvly&ef op&n&omlu
 bdvly&ef Bullyiom;oni taumif;qm [kajymum;on/ Bullyiapmi lewfoomf Ohtay:
 &eni k&zon/ vnf;bdyw&eftwuf Obm;a&onf taumif;qjzpalumi f vuorm;t;
 ajymum;\ / , ifwE&D\ &eni k&zraalumi h vnf;bdjyky&ef Bullyicwv&nyd vnf;bd
 tywfyky&ef Oht outc&on/ xhalmi h &eni k&zv f ysup&orh &eni k&xm;rbrsm;yif
 jzpaon/ (r? 2? 301/)

txufazmfycsurm;uMunjcif;t;zi h onf;cjci f \ tust&ES h onf;cjci f \
 tjyplwul o&em;vnfyd jcEh w&m;vufull fxm; usi b&rnq&w f tyg, fi &bl rus
 a&mutb ok w&fsm; o&bm a&mu&Eh fnfjzpaon/

edh

azmfycly&aom]trsubja&; cEh q;} [bn h olawoepmwr;wof onf;cjci f ES h
 ywouf tcef(1)wof b&m;tavmi fawnES homOursm;\cEh p&f&n&fsm;? tcef(2)wof
 onf;cjci f \ tust&ES h onf;cjci f \ tjypt&alumi f wul y#uwawm&fsm;xrs vuvsf
 rbrs &raz&kwelwif wifcygon/ xh&raz&zm&kwf &mwof cEh onf o&w&m;ig;yg;
 (okw&ed 279/) teuf av;yg;ajrmuf cEh Da&m [li vntaumi? em, u*P&ajcmufyg;
 (avmuedw& 9 (*gxm-1)teuf wpyg;ajrmuf crm - onf;cjci f [li vntaumi?
 tm;&pyg; (t& 3/ 58/) teuf &pyg;ajrmuf cEh vm orP jA [P - &aok [etw&N
 tiftm;um; onf;cjci f [li vntaumi? ritusi hv&m;q, yg; (Zm? 2/ 97/) teuf
 uhyg;ajrmuf cEh onf;ch [li vntaumi? yg&rdq, yg; (r [m&kyw&lyy h f)? 18/) teuf
 ajcmufyg;ajrmuf cEh - ob&mrS v&v&ajrmufalumi f t&xtonf;ch [li vntaumi?
 r*fvmw&m;onq, &pyg; (ck u/ 4/) teuf E&f&q, k&epyg;ajrmuf cEh p-onf;c&jci f
 onfvntaumi? to&odyg&e&onlu Munjcif;t;zi h cEh v&m;\ ta&ygyul o&ri f
 E h ygon/ xhalmi hcEh b&om onf;ch f&f&sm t&m&mwof lu&by&f;csrf;omapE h ygon/

ppmwr;\ tcef(1)wof azmfyxm;aom tavmi fawn&awr;foni r, f
 awm& [mi f x&csu&apmi lewfor&\ow&y;csuft& t&m&monf;cEh bo&zi h atmi f ricyh
 aO&E&mrif&u&onvnt jzpa&y:chom a'gop&vul x&ef;csy&f&f&bl vu&v
 jyer&ygu avm&v&mw&E&szm tust, kw&apE h y h cEh Dg' &aob&vnt r&f&usi b&h
 aom cEh v&m;u h tq&x&vul&fxm; usi b&h&f; y&v&lu h Munh&z&G f aw&E h ygon/
 q' eq&irif;Zmwawm&vnt jzpa&y:cbnh a'gop&vul ou&f;tay: Munh&on&v&v&zi h
 onf;cEh ch&alumi f o&E h ygon/ r&f&tp&f;u h a'go&zi h to&h&cs&bl onf;ch cbnh
 tavmi fawnf oclygve*g;rit&alumi f u&vnt, Munh&z&G f o&E h ygon/

wpz&f&t *z&om&u&bu&w&pyg;jzpa&om t&S f&om&dy&kw&mrax&jr&w&bu&\ onf;ch
 jci f w&m;uhyg;u&vnt v&lu&emt&wk z&G f o&E h ygon/ t&S f&P&ax&&bu&\ yw&Def
 usi ul taumi f jri Dg' jzi h onf;cEh y&lu&vnt, Munh&z&G f o&E h ygon/ r&f&w&f t&E h f

wluEh faomt pff&bnh oLum; rifo ni pp&hol to&m \ qh&;rlul rwe frvlyf onfc h
Eh chLumi f; u haw qri b&E: Nu&NyD jzplygon/

wpzef tcef(2)wGf onfcjci f\ tust? onfcrcjci f\ tjyplwES h ywbufr
umV, u@DwR a0a' [dUmOwR zEeZmw? t* kvtmv& [efawmftaLumi f? ' ICbmPu
rax&ES h taumoubm& ' gZOWkwlwif awEh lygon/ vES lbvt onfcjci fr& b0
tququf &Eji kZcMuojzi h &elwrat; E h ylu h umV, u@DwR vnfau mi f? omrme f
tm; jzi h Et; n b d f a r O a , mi & h o m v n f , ywD e f , u s i N & l u t w r t b a o m f o n f r c E h b o n h
a0a' [dUmOwR S t f & S f \ r a u m i f o w i f y E E h y h o p u l l f a j c m u f u h f a y : u s o n f u h
o n f r c h & E j i k Z r b o j z i h E p D E p z u & E j i k Z R y l u h z E e Z m w l w f v n f a u m i f ? ' g , u m
r s m ; \ x h E s u t s u l u b n f c h v l t r s m ; t u s h o , f y h c b o n h t * k v t m v & [e f a w m f t a L u m i f ?
o n f c h r & h o m a l l u m i h a ' g o u i f j y b c s r f o m & o n h ' I C b m P u r a x & t a L u m i f E S h j r w p h
b & m ; & S N o n f c h a w m r j c i f a L u m i h b m & ' g Z y P h ; u y i f M u n f h y D o m o e m a w m u
& [e f j y k o j z i h & [E h j z p & o n f t x d t u s h u D r m ; a L u m i f w l u h a w q r i b & S M u n f h c L u j y D
j z p l y g o n /

tcsyftm; jzi h j p l w & S n ? Z b e f o n f n n f c h j y l e f t & m & m } [h o m p u m ; o n f
o m r m e f v w l t w l u f t a j y m v G h o m v n f u s i & e t u t h o m t & m j z p l y g o n / x h L u m i h
b & m ; & S l u a ' g o r x l u b l o n f c E h b o r h a t m i e h c h o m p p y l u h a t m i E h b o j z p a L u m i f
a [m L u m ; c j c i f j z p l y g o n / o h o m v n f w w E h b a v m u f r o t f b i j z p a y : a e a o m a v m b r s m ;
t p e f r x l u & e f w p z u b o m ; u h x c l u e p e m a p E h h o m a ' g o w l u h t o w & m ; u h q n f y t j y D
w & m ; t o & t m i v y & e f v l y g o n / o h s o m t o w & m ; & h b a v m u ? w & m ; t o d & h b a v m u f
a v m b ? a ' g o r s m ; a e m u b q l w b o h ; r n i j z p l y g o n / c E b n f j i t f c s r j y D a r w a o n a t ; j r
y g o n / v E S h v c s i f q u l q & m u a r w a E S t c E h w & m ; E p l y g ; v h v u l u h f x m ; u s i b o h r n f
q h v s i f t & m & m o n f a t ; c r f o m , m a e a w m r n i j z p l y g o n /

Oyrm tm; jzi h u e f r m a & ; t w l u f a q ; o n l v t t y l y g o n / a q ; u h t e m a & m * g j z p a y :
v m r S o h a q m i j c i f x u f M u h w i l u m u G j c i f o n i t u s h j z p x e f a p y g o n / t u , l i
r u m u G r i d j z p a y : v m y g u v n f a q ; u h h a q m i f r D j y g u t e m a & m * g r s m ; u h a v s m l u s
a y s m u l u i f o h ; a t m i f p e f a q m i E h l y g o n / x l u b o l y i f a v m u v l a b m i l u t r s u b a ' g o u h
j z p a y : v m r S x e f c s y j c i f x u f r j z p r l u o n f c j c i f w & m ; u h v u l u h f x m ; y g u a & m * g r j z p r d
a q ; u h M u h w i r D j c i f E S h w l y g o n / x h t c g a & m * g a 0 ' e m ' P f r c p m ; & o u b h a v m b ? a ' g o ?
a r m [w & m ; w l N y a v m i r l u t c p m ; & j c i f r & b l j i t f a t ; E h l y g o n / x h L u m i h p p m w r f i , j z i h
a v m u b v o m ; w l N t r s u b a j y a p a & ; t w l u f c E h h o m a q ; w p c l u f u h a o m u b h o i h a L u m i f
w i f y v l u & y g o n /

auşZiwiivîn

p p m w r f j z p a j r m u b a t m i f p p O h a q m i & l u f a y : y g a o m w m O e c l y g a r m u e s y f q & m l u D
a ' g u l v m r i f a t m i E S h ' k v d y g a r m u e s y f q & m r l u D a ' g u l v m & i & i b e f w l t m ; v n f a u m i f ?
p p m w r f u h j y i l q i l j z n l o u l M u h M u y a y : y g a o m t a & S w l f y n m X m e r S y g a r m u (X m e r S) q & m r l u D
a ' g u l v m O i f O i f & D t m ; v n f a u m i f ? t z u z u r S O h f O e f u h D y l l a y : c h u y g a o m t a & S w l f y n m X m e r S
q & m ? q & m r r s m ; t m ; v h w l t m ; v n f a u m i f t x t y i f a u s Z i w i & y g o n /

urɸuɸn&iɸ

ygVáwnɸ t | uxɸnEsh Esh tjcɸurɸrɸɸ

cl' uygygVáwnɸ (1962)/ &efuleɸ omoema&;OɸpɸXmeyEɸyɸwɸlɸlɸ/

p&ɸ myɸ#ut | uxɸɸl (1958)/ &efuleɸ omoema&;OɸpɸXmeyEɸyɸwɸlɸlɸ/

Zmwu | uxɸm(wwá, mbma*g)/(1959)/ &efuleɸ omoema&;OɸpɸXmeyEɸyɸwɸlɸlɸ/

Zmwu | uxɸm(pwáwmbma*g)/(1959)/ &efuleɸ omoema&;OɸpɸXmeyEɸyɸwɸlɸlɸ/

Zmwu | uxɸm(yOármmbma*g)/(1959)/ &efuleɸ omoema&;OɸpɸXmeyEɸyɸwɸlɸlɸ/

Zmwu | uxɸm(qa | mbma*g)/(1959)/ &efuleɸ omoema&;OɸpɸXmeyEɸyɸwɸlɸlɸ/

Zmwu | uxɸm(owármmbma*g)/(1959)/ &efuleɸ omoema&;OɸpɸXmeyEɸyɸwɸlɸlɸ/

ZmwuygVd(yXarmbma*g)/(1960)/ &efuleɸ omoema&;OɸpɸXmeyEɸyɸwɸlɸlɸ/

ZmwuygV('kwá, mbma*g)/(1960)/ &efuleɸ omoema&;OɸpɸXmeyEɸyɸwɸlɸlɸ/

anmiɸueɸq&mawɸmb&m;lɸlɸ/ (2006)/ &efuleɸ r*ɸwá:ɸyeɸ ciɸk&ɸɸpɸmay(p-lɸlɸt)

"rɸy' t | uxɸm(yXarmbma*g)/(1958)/ &efuleɸ omoema&;OɸpɸXmeyEɸyɸwɸlɸlɸ/

"rɸy' t | uxɸm('kwá, mbma*g)/(1958)/ &efuleɸ omoema&;OɸpɸXmeyEɸyɸwɸlɸlɸ/

"rɸy' ygVáwnɸ (2000)/ &efuleɸ omoema&;OɸpɸXmeyEɸyɸwɸlɸlɸ/

rZáryPɸhót | uxɸɸl (1957)/ &efuleɸ omoema&;OɸpɸXmeyEɸyɸwɸlɸlɸ/

rZáryPɸhóygVáwnɸ (2000)/ &efuleɸ omoema&;OɸpɸXmeyEɸyɸwɸlɸlɸ/

r[moáwOɸb(t&ɸɸ) (1963)/ &efuleɸ [ɸmOwáɸyEɸyɸwɸlɸlɸ/

r[mO*ɸygVáwnɸ (2000)/ &efuleɸ omoema&;OɸpɸXmeyEɸyɸwɸlɸlɸ/

rɸvyPɸhót | uxɸm(yXarmbma*g)/(1957)/ &efuleɸ omoema&;OɸpɸXmeyEɸyɸwɸlɸlɸ/

rɸvyPɸhót | uxɸm('kwá, mbma*g)/(1957)/ &efuleɸ omoema&;OɸpɸXmeyEɸyɸwɸlɸlɸ/

rɸvyPɸhóygVáwnɸ (2000)/ &efuleɸ omoema&;OɸpɸXmeyEɸyɸwɸlɸlɸ/

vɸl&n(armiɸ) (2010)/ &efuleɸ omoema&;OɸpɸXmeyEɸyɸwɸlɸlɸ/

o*gxɸmO*ɸed geO*ɸáɸ kváygVá (1999)/ &efuleɸ omoema&;OɸpɸXmeyEɸyɸwɸlɸlɸ/

oáwɸEɸO*ɸygVáwnɸ (2005)/ &efuleɸ omoema&;OɸpɸXmeyEɸyɸwɸlɸlɸ/

oáwáɸdgwvygVá (1999)/ &efuleɸ omoema&;OɸpɸXmeyEɸyɸwɸlɸlɸ/

lɸbbmombOɸb(t&ɸɸ) (2010)/ oáwɸeɸrɸr*ɸyOɸɸuɸrɸ/ &efuleɸ omoema&;Oɸpɸ XmeyEɸyɸwɸlɸlɸ/

t*ɸwá&ygVáwnɸ('lueɸygu)/(2000)/ &efuleɸ omoema&;OɸpɸXmeyEɸyɸwɸlɸlɸ/

t*ɸwá&ygVáwnɸ(wáueɸygu)/(2000)/ &efuleɸ omoema&;OɸpɸXmeyEɸyɸwɸlɸlɸ/

t(armiɸ)-r[mOZáɸ? báá/ (1995)/ r*ɸwámed geɸ/ &efuleɸ omoema&;OɸpɸXmeyEɸyɸwɸlɸlɸ/

O'geɸt | uxɸɸl (1958)/ &efuleɸ omoema&;OɸpɸXmeyEɸyɸwɸlɸlɸ/

Oy&ɸyPɸhóygVáwnɸ (2000)/ &efuleɸ omoema&;OɸpɸXmeyEɸyɸwɸlɸlɸ/